

Coping Strategies of Parents / Home Makers in Facing Challenges of Insecurity and Kidnapping / Banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for Healthy Family Living

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Abstract

The study examined the coping strategies of parents/ home maker in facing challenges of insecurity, Kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Areas of Rivers State for healthy family living. The study made - use of three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses. Survey design was adopted for the study and all the household members in Ahoada Local Government area formed the population. While stratified random sampling technique was used to select 323 respondents (200 females, and 123 males., Questionnaires was the instrument for data collection and a four-point rating scale was used to elicit information from the respondents ranging from strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). Two research assistants assisted the researchers for administration and collection of the copies of the instrument. The instrument was validated by three experts and the reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha Index. The data collected from research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while t-test was used to test the hypothesis. The following findings were made among others to include, adequate involvement in agriculture, establishment of small scale businesses, embarking on savings and investments, encouraging family members to work, avoid being lazy and extravagant etc. Recommendations were made based on the findings to include, parents / home makers should endeavor to make investments on agriculture in order to meet the challenges of food insecurity, parents / home makers should sensitize the family members on security tips encouraging family members to be involved in entrepreneurship skills that will help them not to remain idle, provision of vocational skills to help family members to be useful and functional members of the society.

Keywords: Coping strategies, challenges, insecurity, banditry, healthy family living.

INTRODUCTION

Insecurity is a fundamental problem in human existence. It exists both in family and wider section of the society and a major problem of life. Currently, it is a wider problem of the whole world whether Nigeria, there are several cases of insecurity ranging from kidnapping and other related activities of banditry. This social problem is becoming an impediment to every parent or homemakers in their responsibility to provide necessary ingredient needed in family development. Consequently, several options and strategies have been adopted to cope with security challenge to no avail especially in the North East where insecurity is on increase. It is necessary for parent at this point in time at the study area to make necessary plan require alleviating this problem.

Onyema (2010) maintain that to secure mean to be free from danger or any harm and anxiety. However, Akihomen (2010) pointed out that security is not the absent of threat but ability to respond to security breaches and threat and experience in need and in practice, principle through the use of coping strategies and principles; measure or planning in other to strengthen security of life and properties in individual families. Insecurity is a basic problem of man which necessitates the need for parent involvement in providing security tips to member family. It is import to note that parent is the head of the family and it is responsibility to provide enabling environment to achieve the necessary security

measures to cope with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry. It is also a responsibility of every parent in families to adopt adequate plans to maximize profit and generate resources that will maintenance and development of families, to also adopt measure in other to reduce the risk of wastage in every family so as to meet the need of the whole family etc.

Hassan 2016 Security is perceived as a basic human need that contributes to effective learning. Psychologists proposed that security is crucial for human survival. According to the hierarchy of Needs postulated by Abraham Maslow, the lower needs of man like food, shelter and security must be met before other higher needs like education or intellectual/cognitive needs.

Inability to satisfy the need for security may cause stress in individuals and hinder them from pursuing higher level needs.

Generally, security implies safety, freedom from danger and protection from physical harm. Human beings are instinctively driven to maximize available resources in ensuring their physical, physiological and psychological well-being. Security is not limited to protection from physical harm. Security also involves existence of environmental factors that instill peace of mind in an individual in order to empower him/her function effectively in the society. Poor human relations between teacher and student can hamper students' mental health and cause insecurity. Poor infrastructural designs at home can expose students to insecurity problems like health hazards and stress. Some female students feel threatened as a result of rampant incidences of sexual abuse and rape in schools and the society.

Shuaibu therefore submitted that a safe school is one that fosters peaceful, positive or cordial relationships among families.

Concept of Insecurity: Insecurity is concerned with feelings of uncertainty, dangers or threats to life. According to Hassan (2016) insecurity is a negative feeling involving fear, anxiety, uncertainty and injustice, among others. When an individual does not have control over a situation but has to rely on the cooperation of others that cannot be guaranteed, the result may be frustration or insecurity. Insecurity is a threat to learning. Prevailing peace or conflict within communities around the schools often has triple effects on the teaching and learning activities of such schools etc. New English Dictionary (2010) insecurity is a state of being to danger or threat, or uncertainty anxiety about oneself, or lack of protection. Insecurity also define as lack of confident or state of being subject is danger, vulnerability, lack of assurance or confidence especially in regard to oneself.

Parents: Cambrge dictionary define parents as a noun, a mother, father, or father of a person. New London Dictionary define as one who begat someone, or birth or adoptive mother, a father, or a biological father of a child born or concerned during the father marriage, to birth mother, or the unmarried biological father who concerted to the adoption of the child.

Udom (2011) Parent are the one who begat offspring or one who occupy the role of mother or father. Parent they are caregiver of offspring in other especially to human being or guidance.

Homemaker: New Website Dictionary define homemaker as the one who manage home, homemaker is the one who managed household of one family, spent and occupy the family responsibility. Homemaker act and oversee day to day operation and responsibility of the house. She is the one who maintain the upkeeping and management of day to day especially spouses.

Challenge: New Website Dictionary define challenge as to engage in contest or dispute and validity of responsibility, call to prove or testify for quality, call for someone to participate in composition, or situation of fight to decide who is superiors in term of ability or strength.

Strategies: New London Dictionary define as strategies as a plan of action design to achieve a set goal in term of overall aims, or plan to develop coherent economic measure.

Strategies define as planning and developing overall military operation and movement in war or battle.

Wikipedia define as strategies careful developed plan or method for aching a goods or skill in developing issues. Also see it as general plan to achieved one or more long term or overall good under condition.

CAUSES OF INSECURITY

According to Oxford Research Group (ORG) there are perhaps four most important underlying drivers of insecurities: a) Climate change b) Increasing competition over resources c) Global militarization d) Marginalisation across much of the 'majority world

A Changing Climate

The issue of global climate change has become prominent over recent decades, growing to be seen by many in the environmental movement as a problem of apocalyptic proportions (Lean, 2005).

Climate change is a complex phenomenon, which will have multiple and non-linear effects on human security. It will have both direct and indirect impacts on the stability and security of states and communities particularly the Global South.

Sea level rises and desertification are two processes for which climate change is a catalyst. Both are likely to affect regions that have not been heavy contributors to green-house gas emission levels; both are processes that will make some hitherto inhabited areas unfit for human habitation. This also increases the chances of conflicts of 'the commons' due to migration.

COMPETITION OVER RESOURCES

North-South Engagement

Competition over energy resources increases the chances and facilitation of conflict between the West-consumer nations and the resource-rich nations in the south. Energy the current focus on extremism in Sub-Saharan Africa, have all raised difficult issues to be addressed. Such instances are a) Deep water military aggression: China and the Pacific - China's recent actions in the South China Sea and Himalayas have given rise to further—and at times violent— conflict over the region's natural resources. And b) the increased use of drones and its impact on increased conflict: by USA and its allies in Yemen Iraq Pakistan etc.; this has also influenced the de-monopolization by non-US allied states like Iran Sudden and Syria and non-state actors like Hamas, Hezbollah and the Islamic State.

Marginalization of the Majority World

Divisions between the rich industrialized North and the 'majority world' are a key and intensifying driver of global insecurity. While overall global wealth has increased, the benefits of this economic growth have not been equally shared. The rich-poor divide is growing, with a heavy concentration of growth in regions of North America and Europe in particular, and the 'majority world' of Asia, Africa and Latin America (UNDP, 2009). Example is the rise of drug trafficking in the Afro-Colombian communities of the Curvarado and Jiguamiando in the Urabá region. Also marginalization of the "Mandera Triangle" in the Kenya, Ethiopia and Somalia borders by the their central government leading to their high vulnerable to periodic droughts and floods, high levels of poverty, long-term disruption to the traditional systems of livelihood, ongoing inter-clan conflicts and border tensions between states.

Deepening oppression and political exclusion amongst communities in the South combine with poverty and discrimination to present an increasingly dynamic threat to national and international stability. Also poverty has played its role to marginalize as seen in issues of food insecurity among the poorer nations. For example, chronic food insecurity in Baluchistan (Pakistan) has 'aggravated the sense of marginalisation', encouraging the rise of insurgency groups.

Challenge of insecurity

Insecurity has cripple economic activities in Nigeria especially in the affected area of operation, it has also led to the migration of people from the affected area to the other part of the country, this has also the freedom of people and denied the rights them of citizenship. The nation newspaper (2013) maintain that how the activities of Banditry has hinder economic activities the country. Thousands of people have died owing to the ugly effect of the insecurity.

This insecurity has also led to abandonment of people business and reduction of people patronage of product, some led to the retrenchment of workers and numbers of workers and hours of operations - leadership newspaper June 14 (2013). Insecurity also lead to reduction of government derivation from affected region as result of youth restiveness in those place as well as reduction of in investment and growth of business in the affected place without excluding government executed project.

Review of related Empirical Studies

The study of Uzoh and Nwakwo (2012) examined the coping strategies of parent during inflation and depression on home management in Enugu State. Two research question and two null hypotheses guided the study, 4 objectives was used. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, with a total population of 1230 respondent comprising several home in the Slate with the sample size of 300 respondent made up of 115 families 217 household was drawn from the study population using the satisfied random sampling techniques. 18 item structural questioner waited on 4point rating scale was used as data collecting instrument that was used, and was validated by two expert in borne economics department with reliability index of 0.89 was obtain in text re-text method using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. The Research question was administer and answer using means and retain statistics was used to test null hypothesis at the probability level of 5%. The finding show that inflation contribute to economic crisis and also become a malady to home management in the study area and also Government need to monitory measures for prize

stability and also suggest a possible solution which the introduction of fiscal policy to end the persistent increase an exchange rate.

The study of Mohammed & Useni (2016) examining effective strategies in managing resource among families in Kaduna State. The total population of the study was 1,000,200 with the sample of size of 300): The study was guided by 4 specific objective and 3 research question, and three research hypothesis method of data collection were used which are interview and questionnaire and documentary method data was analyzed using both quantitative and qualitatively. The research adopts standard derivation and Z-test as method of data analyzes. Findings reveal that Government has a lot to do in providing an enabling environment for families in helping them to cope with available secured resource by building enable environment for families and homemakers to cope with problem secured and resource also adopt maintained management and proper strategies' of managing secured resources among families in the areas.

The study of Adam & Ugochi (2006) conducted survey on straggles of managing the effect of broken home on academic performance of children in Enugu State, the study aims at accessing the effect of psychological problem of divorce on children in Enugu State. The study makes use of 5 objectives, 5 research questions, and 5 research hypotheses. The study adopt quasi experimental design as a method a product person coloration moment was employ as a method data analysis, the total population of 1,200 was using as a sample size of 300 was also chosen. Marxian political theory was employ as a theoretical framework in the study. 300 copies of questionnaire was administered and retrieved therefore it was conclude that broken home affect the academic performance of children in Enugu State and factors like lack of communication among parent, poverty, infertility, lack of trust, persistent querying, etc. among other factors was responsible. Therefore, it was recommended that couple should always channel their problem to marriage councilors and also seek advice from God for solution.

Dagogo & Nnamdi (2010) carried out a survey on the influence of family brake down and welfare of children in Rivers State. The study aimed at assessing the impact of the family brake down on welfare of children in Rivers State. The study make use of 3 object, 3 research questions, 3 research hypothesis, the total population of 1,500 was used and a sample size of 250 was also used. The functionist theory was employ as a theoretical framework for the study and descriptive survey method was using for the investigation. Expo factors was chosen as a design for the study, and ordinarily list square regression was chosen as method of data analysis. 250 copies of questionnaire was administered and retrieve successfully, data was source from both primary and secondary source, related concept were reviewed and it was conclude that family brake down have psychological and detrimental effect on well fare of children in Rivers State, so therefore it was recommended that children welfare and upbringing should not be left in the hand of parent alone and it will be a share responsibility between parent and government. Programme should be conducted by government to educate parent on their responsibility of welfare of their children.

The study of Ugochukwu & Uzoh) carried out a study on effect of marital instability on children academic performance in Nnewi Local Government Area, Anambra State. The study aims at the impact of marital instability and the resultant effect on children academic performance in Nnewi Local Government Area, Anambra State. 4 objectives were used in the study, 4 research questions and 4 research hypotheses were also used in the study. Total population of 800 people was chosen and Taro Yemein formular was employ to determine the sample size of 200. Descriptive survey method was useful as a method for the investigation and content analysis was chosen as a design for the study. Total copies of 200 questionnaires was administered and restive with the aid of researcher and friend. Family resource theory was employed as a theoretical framework for the study, standard deviation, z-test and simple percentage was employed as method of data analysis, therefore it was concluded that marital instability have a psychological effect on children academic performance in Nnewi Local Government Area, Anambra State, base on this it was recommended that there Government should sensitized couple by organizing seminars on marriage in other to educate them. Associated factor like lack of communication, lack of truths, lack of respect among others are the fundamental causes for marital instability.

Statement of Problem

The focus of this study is to examine the coping strategies of parents / homemakers in facing challenge of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living. It also involves the relationship between the coping strategies and the challenge of kidnapping / banditry in the study area. There are several cases of kidnapping and banditry as well as other related social problem which has serious implication on security management of parent in the study area. Social problems which include kidnapping, stealing, prostitution, hostage , this problems are on increase, affecting economic activities and other related development plan e.g investment, skill acquisition programme as well as its negative impact of management of individual family. Parent in their responsibility to provide secure and comfortable environment for family members are now finding it difficult as a result of this crises.

Food crises is one of the major problem of insecurity in the means of insecure environment, parent also ponder over choice in their responsibility to families by providing the necessary requirement needed for the development and

maintenance of families, shelter, protection and other are necessary roles of parent in families. Some parent find it difficult to meet up with this need in the family. It is obvious with adequate security tips, sensitization, another related strategies, parent from different families in the study area can face the challenges of insecurity / kidnapping, banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for Healthy family living.

Purpose

The main purpose of this study is to examine coping strategies of parents / homemakers in facing challenge of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living.

This purpose includes:

1. To examine the strategies of creating adequate plans for food supply to cope with challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living .
2. To examine the strategies of teaching and adopting adequate entrepreneurship skills in coping with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living.
3. To examine the strategies of providing adequate security tips through sensitization, education and knowledge to cope with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living

Research Question

The study is guiding by the following research questions

1. What are the strategies of creating adequate plans in other to cope with challenge of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living.
2. What are the strategies and adopting adequate entrepreneurship skills in coping with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living.
3. What are the strategies of providing adequate security tips through sensitization, education and knowledge to cope with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living .

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant differences on the mean score of the respondent on the strategies of creating adequate plans for food supply to cope with challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living.

H₀₂: There is no significant differences on the mean score of the respondent on the strategies of teaching and adopting adequate entrepreneurship skills in coping with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living.

H₀₃: There is no significant differences on the mean score of the respondent on the strategies of providing adequate security tips through sensitization, education and knowledge to cope with insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family Living .

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study: Descriptive survey design was used for the study, according to Godwin in Nwogu (2016) a survey research is a one in which a group of people or items is study by analyzing data from few people or item consider to be representative of entire group. The design is considered appropriate because it is useful in gathering data about opinions and record of event that can be analyzed and interpret to measure relationship between variables and any manipulation.

Area of Study: Ahoada East Local Government Area is chosen as area of study. Ahoada East is a Local Government Area in Rivers State Nigeria. Ahoada East is located at North West in a city of Port Harcourt. It seat is in the city of Ahoada. The Local Government was created in 1996 from the whole Ahoada of Akinima town with the population density of 474.56% of annual population change. Estimated population of Ahoada is 340.567 inhabitant. MPC National Population (2006), their occupation include farming, fishing. The following communities make up the local government Odiabidi, Abarikpo, Ogbo, Ihuowo, Ahoada, Ihuaba, Idoke, Edeoha.

Population of the Study: The population of this study comprise of all household families in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State. The total population of this study is made up of 340.567. Inhabitants.

Sample and Sampling Techniques: A simple random sampling techniques was used as a techniques to selected (8) communities from Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State. These were as technique to select 8 communities from Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State this was to produces a sample sizes.

Subsequently the stratified random sampling was used to select the total household families for the study. 323 household families were selected as sample size for the study.

Instrument for data collection self-developed and structured questionnaire tagged Coping Strategies of Parents/Homemakers in facing insecurity, kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family living was used to select data for the study. It was validated by three (3) experts from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The liability was tested using Crombach Alpha yielded 0.82 which shows high level of reliability of instrument and hypotheses that shows the guide to the study. The questionnaire was design and modified on 4 point rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D) Strongly Agreed (DA).

Method of Data Collection: Direct contact method was used to collect data with the help of two research assistance who help to administer the instrument to respondent. The method of administration and collection of instrument was desirable and acceptable.

Method of Data Analysis: Mean score and standard deviation was used in answering the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Any weighted mean score which weighted mean score that is above an indication of high level of phenomenon under study;

RESULT

The result of the survey is presented in tables below:

Research question 1: What are the strategies adopted by parents in creating adequate plans for food supply in other to coup with challenges facing insecurity / kidnapping in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family leaving

Table-1: Mean and Standard deviation on strategies adopted by parents in creating adequate plans for food supply in other to coup with challenges facing insecurity / kidnapping in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family leaving.

S/N	ITEMS Strategies for adequate food supply	Female N=200			Male N=123		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Adequate Investment on Agriculture	3.49	.77	Agree	3.10	.87	Agree
2	Small Scale Business	3.11	1.00	Agree	3.03	.73	Agree
3	Saving and Investment	3.10	.91	Agree	3.13	.83	Agree
4	Encourage member family to work	3.12	1.03	Agree	3.08	.91	Agree
5	Avoid laziness and extravagant life	3.28	.71	Agree	3.10	.79	Agree
	Grand mean	3.22	0.88		3.09	0.83	

Key: \bar{x} = Mean Score; SD = Standard Deviation; A = Agree; D = Disagree

Table one above shows the Mean rating and standard deviation of respondent on the strategies of parent in creating adequate plan for food supply to coup with challenges of insecurity in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

The data shows that all the items from 1 – 5 had weighted the mean score above criterion means 2.50 and thus were agree because he has grand mean score of 3.085. In summary, with aggregate weighted mean and standard deviation of 2.50, it is evidence that the respondent agree that adequate investment on agriculture (3.10), small scale business 93.03), Savings and investment (3.13), encouraging member families to work (3.08), avoid leaving extravagant life (3.10) are coping strategies of parent / home makers in facing challenges of insecurity in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Research question 2: What are strategies of teaching and adopting adequate entrepreneur skill in facing challenges if insecurity and kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State

Table-2: Means and standard deviation on strategies of teaching and adopting adequate entrepreneur skill in facing challenges if insecurity and kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State

S/N	Items Strategies of adopting entrepreneurship	Female N=200			Male N=123		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
6	Investment in Poultry skill	3.19	.77	Agree	3.04	.88	Agree
7	Encourage member to seek for capital for entrepreneurship	3.28	.84	Agree	3.18	.88	Agree

8	Encouraging member to enroll in clothing business	3.22	.85	Agree	3.02	.88	Agree
9	Encourage member to enroll in online business	3.24	.85	Agree	3.06	.87	Agree
10	Open belt king business	2.79	1.14	Agree	2.63	.87	Agree
	Grand mean	3.23	0.82		3.07	0.88	

Key: \bar{x} = Mean Score; SD = Standard Deviation; A = Agree; D = Disagree

The data in table Two above shows the mean rating and standard deviation on response on the Parents strategies of teaching, adequate entrepreneur skills to face challenges of insecurity and kidnapping / banditry in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State for healthy family living with criterion mean of (2.50) thus were agree.

In summary, with aggregate weighted mean above criterion mean of (2.50), it is evidence that the respondent agree that, participation in poultry skill, (3.04) encouraging members to have capital for entrepreneur skills (3.18), encouraging members to enroll in clothing business (3.02), encouraging member to engage in Online business (3.06), Encouraging member to open belt king business (2.63). All these are parents strategies adopted in facing insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Research question 3: What are strategies of proving adequate security tips through sensitization, education and knowledge in facing insecurity and kidnapping / banditry by parent in providing healthy family living in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State?

Table-3: Mean and Standard deviation of strategies of proving adequate security tips through sensitization, education and knowledge in facing insecurity and kidnapping / banditry by parent in providing healthy family living in Ahoada East Local Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Female N=200			Male N=123		
		\bar{x}	SD	Decision	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
11	Sensitize the member's family on danger of insecurity and kidnapping / banditry.	3.23	.74	Agree	2.98	.83	Agree
12	Engage the member family through peace talk to avoid mixed up with people of questionable character or harbouring terrorist.	3.28	.70	Agree	3.21	.69	Agree
13	Empower the family member through vocational skills to avoid bring mind to violence or kidnapping related issues	3.07	.86	Agree	3.01	.84	Agree
14	Give them proper and structure education so that they can know the negative confidence of kidnapping and banditry.	3.02	.89	Agree	2.99	.85	Agree
15	Teach them to security expert so that they can mentor others.	3.16	.86	Agree	3.06	.86	Agree
	Grand mean	3.15	0.81		3.05	0.81	

Key: \bar{x} = Mean Score; SD = Standard Deviation; A = Agree; D = Disagree

The data in table 3 above chows that mean rating and standard deviation of respondent on the strategies of parent proving adequate security tips through sensitization, education, knowledge in facing challenge of insecurity in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for Healthy family living. The weighted mean score above criterion mean of (2.50) thus was agree.

In summary, with aggregate weighted mean above the criterion mean of (2.50), it is evidence that the respondent agree on Sensitize the members family on danger of insecurity and kidnapping / banditry (2.98), Engage the member family through peace talk to avoid mixed up with people of questionable character or harbouring terrorist. (3.21), Empower the family member through vocational skills to avoid bring mind to violence or kidnapping related issues (3.01), Give them proper and structure education so that they can know the negative confidence of kidnapping and banditry (2.99), Teach them to security expert so that they can mentor others (3.06). All are coping strategies of parent / home makers in facing challenges if insecurity, kidnapping / banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Result Test of Hypotheses

The three (3) hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean score of the respondent on the strategies of creating adequate plans for food supply in other to face the challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Table4: t-test analysis of means respondent on male and female respondent on parent strategies on adequate plans for food supply in other to face the challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living

Category	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Level of Significant	Decision
Female	200	3.22	0.88	321	1.4	± 1.96	0.05	Ho is retained
Male	123	3.09	0.83					

A critical look at the table 4 shows a summary of means, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean scores of male and female respondent on the parent strategies on adequate plans for food supply in other to face the challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living

The z-test statistics calculated and used in testing the hypothesis stood at 1.4 while the critical z-test value stood at ± 1.96 , using 321 degree of freedom at 0.5 alpha level of significance. Since the z-cal is less than the z-crit value, the null hypothesis (H₀) is therefore upheld. That is $z\text{-cal} < z\text{-crit} = 1.4 < \pm 1.96$, at 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondent on parent strategies on adequate plans for food supply in other to face the challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean score of respondent on the strategies of adopting teaching of entrepreneurship skills by parents in other to face challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Table 5: z-test analysis of the difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondent on the on the strategies of adopting teaching of entrepreneurship skills by parents in other to face challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Category	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Level of Significant	Decision
Female	200	3.23	0.82	321	1.7	± 1.96	0.05	Ho is retained
Male	132	3.07	0.88					

A critical look at the table 5 shows a summary of means, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean scores of male and female respondent on the strategies of adopting teaching of entrepreneurship skills by parents in other to face challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

The z-test statistics calculated and used in testing the hypothesis stood at 1.7 while the critical z-test value stood at ± 1.96 , using 321 degree of freedom at 0.5 alpha level of significance. Since the z-cal is less than the z-crit value, the null hypothesis (H₀) is therefore upheld. That is $z\text{-cal} < z\text{-crit} = 1.7 < \pm 1.96$, at 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondent on the strategies of adopting teaching of entrepreneurship skills by parents in other to face challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean score of the respondent on the parent strategies on security tips, sensitization, education and knowledge in facing insecurity / kidnapping / and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Table-6: z-test analysis of the difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondent on the parent strategies on security tips, sensitization, education and knowledge in facing insecurity / kidnapping / and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Category of Institution	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Level of Significant	Decision
Female	200	3.15	0.81	321	1.1	± 1.96	0.05	Ho is retained
Male	123	3.05	0.81					

A critical look at the table 6 shows a summary of means, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean scores of male and female respondent on the parent strategies on security tips, sensitization, education and knowledge in facing insecurity / kidnapping / and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

The z-test statistics calculated and used in testing the hypothesis stood at 1.1 while the critical z-test value stood at ± 1.96 , using 321 degree of freedom at 0.5 alpha level of significance. Since the z-cal is less than the z-crit value, the null hypothesis (Ho) is therefore upheld. That is $z\text{-cal} < z\text{-crit} = 1.1 < \pm 1.96$, at 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female respondent on the parent strategies on security tips, sensitization, education and knowledge in facing insecurity / kidnapping / and banditry in Ahoada Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that the respondents agreed that Adequate investment on agriculture (3.10), small scale business (3.03), saving and investment (3.13), encourage member family to work (3.08), avoid laziness and extravagant life (3.10) are parent strategies of adopting, adequate plans for food supply in other to face challenges of insecurity / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government area of Rivers State for healthy family living. This finding agrees with the view of Udo and Uche (2013) whose finding shows that social problem of insecurity or kidnapping / banditry are major problem of parent / homemakers in creating a healthy living in families etc.

The second finding of the study review that participation in poultry skills or skill acquisition programme (3.04), encouraging members to have capital for entrepreneurship (3.18), encouraging member to role in clothing business (3.02), encouraging members to enroll in Online business (3.06), Encouraging member to open belt king business (2.63) are strategies adopted by parent in creating adequate entrepreneur skills in facing insecurity challenge / kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers State for healthy family living. The finding agree with the view of Ikenna (2005) opines that security of life and property is a hallmark of parent decision in their responsibility to their families, to sustain families in the time of insecurity, adequate investment is require, saving is require, member families are require to work together to produce food need and the quantity to meet up the need of the family survival at the period of insecurity. Parent also need to provide enabling environment for house hold maintenance, food production, adequate planning is required, economic activities is also require to alleviate problems of parent sensitization on spending policy should also be adopted by family members to avoid wastage of family resource etc.

The final finding of the study revealed that the respondents agreed that sensitizing member family on danger of insecurity and kidnapping / banditry (2.98) engage the member family through peace talk to avoid mixing up with people of unquestionable character or avoid harbouring terrorist (3.21), empower the member through vocational skills to avoid bringing their mind out to violence of issue related to violence or kidnapping related issues (3.01), given them proper education and structure training (2.99), so that they can know the negative consequence of kidnapping or banditry in the environment, teach them to be security expert so that they can mentor others(3.06), these are parent strategies of coping with insecurity challenge and kidnapping and banditry in Ahoada East Local Government of Rivers State for healthy family living. It is a responsibility of every parent in each individual family to teach their children the dangers of insecurity, kidnapping and banditry, parent are to teach their children the important of security of life and property, food security, financial security, security of future etc.

CONCLUSION

The study conclude that security is the most important need of the family, security of life and property, security of resources, food security as well as financial security has a very good role to play in healthy family living, availability of all these factors is happiness of every good families and happy families. It is a need of parent to provide above major strategies in other to coup or face the challenges of insecurity in their domain; sensitization is a key factor when talking of insecurity/ kidnapping and banditry because it involve education and awareness. Parent need to provide Smart Phones for their children so that they can report any outbreak of violence to police or any security agent, members of the family

also need to be sensitized on the consequence of the insecurity and kidnapping, above all, food security, it is a responsibility of parent to make adequate plans for food for the members of the family, members family also need to be sensitized to avoid mixing up with terrorist or people of questionable character, investment or terrorist, this strategy will help parent / homemakers cope with a challenge of insecurity and kidnapping or banditry in Ahoada East Local Government Area of Rivers for healthy family living.

Recommendation

The study makes the following recommendation

- Parent in every family should sensitize their member on the need, create awareness, educate them to aware of insecurity situation on how to cope with it.
- Parent should also make sure that entrepreneur skill should be created and adopted to member of the family as a source of empowerment to be able to cope in an insecure environment, vocational skill should be created to engage member of the family to avoid unnecessary relationship with people of questionable character or terrorist.
- Smart Phone should be provided to member of the family by parent to report any cases of violence or kidnapping and banditry to security agency.
- Members of the family should be empowered with either skill or investment strategies to be able to function in an financial insecure environment. Adequate plan should be made on food security to avoid food crises in an insecure environment.
- Parent in every family should make provision for financial security, resources, structure education should be given to the children to enable them cope in an insecure environment etc.

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